

A Service Provider's Guide to Data Sharing Policies

These reference cards convey data sharing policy recommendations to be adopted by data and service providers within the EOSC-hub consortium. Our recommendations contribute to the developing field of data sharing policies in the EOSC at large.

The Why | The What | **The How**

How can you implement data sharing policies practically? Some examples.

For more details, consult the D2.8 and D2.9 deliverables via: <https://bit.ly/2zDAAnM>

The Five Safes Principles

Within Medical and Health data services, a good domains practice is that of the Five Safes. EOSC-hub should adopt these Five Safes principles as guidance¹⁰ for the management and handling of sensitive data in the EOSC-hub ecosystem.

Domain-specific RDM Protocols

The Domain-specific Research Data Management Protocols for specific communities - for example the Science Europe Guiding Document (2018¹¹) - has been adopted by for example CESSDA and ELIXIR. EOSC-hub stimulates the application of data domain protocols.

NOTES

¹⁰] See <https://bit.ly/2BDO43s> for a good discussion of the principles and current applications

¹¹] via <https://bit.ly/3d4qhaR>